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First record of *Tephritis praecox* (Diptera: Tephritidae), a pest of *Calendula* (Asteraceae), in Slovakia

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Korneyev, S.V., Šalamon, I. & Korneyev, V.A. First record of *Tephritis praecox* (Diptera: Tephritidae), a pest of *Calendula* (Asteraceae), in Slovakia. — *Tephritis praecox* (Loew, 1844) known to infest pot marigold (*Calendula*), a medicine plant used as anti-inflammatory and a remedy for healing wounds, as well as spice, predominantly in the Mediterranean region. It is recorded as a pest of cultivated *Calendula* in Slovakia for the first time. Morphology, phylogenetic relationships, biology and distribution are discussed.

Key words. Diptera, Tephritidae, Asteraceae, *Calendula*, Slovakia.

Корнєєв, С.В., Шаламон, І. і Корнєєв, В.О. Перша знахідка *Tephritis praecox* (Diptera: Tephritidae), шкідника нагідків (Asteraceae), у Словаччині. — *Tephritis praecox* (Леве, 1844), відомий як фітофаг, що розвивається переважно в середземномор'ї у суцвіт'ях нагідків (*Calendula*) — лікарської рослини, яку використовують як протизапальний засіб та засіб для загоєння ран, а також як спеції. У Словаччині вперше зафіксований як шкідник культивованої календули. Обговорюються морфологія, філогенетичні зв'язки, біологія та поширення.

Ключові слова. Diptera, Tephritidae, Asteraceae, *Calendula*, Словаччина.

Introduction

Tephritis praecox (Loew, 1844) is a fly known to occur mostly in Mediterranean region and Atlantic European countries from Great Britain to Greece and Ukraine (Crimean Peninsula), as well as in the Middle East and North Africa from Canary Is. to Afghanistan (Merz & Korneyev, 2004; Norrbom et al. 1999).

Phylogenetic analysis (Korneyev et al., 2020) has shown that *T. praecox* represents a sister lineage to most if not all other species of *Tephritis*, morphologically differing only in having a peculiar wing pattern with three subrectangular hyaline spots forming a line almost

perpendicular to its vein R_{4+5} distally of pterostigma and crossvein r-m. It can be differentiated from *T. luteipes* Merz, 1992, another species with similar wing pattern, by the black katapisternal seta (white in *T. luteipes*) and other characters listed by Merz (1991), as well as by the host plant (*Artemisia* in *T. luteipes* vs. *Calendula* in *T. praecox*).

For a long time, *T. praecox* and *Tephritis poecilura* Loew, 1869 were considered separate species due to differences in the yellow/ black femora and base of abdomen, as well as in tiny differences of their wing patterns, but then Merz (1992) clearly showed by study of material reared from *Calendula arvensis* that they merely represent colour morphs of the same species.

Figs 1–3. *Calendula officinalis* and its pests: 1–2 — garden (1) and field plantations (2), 3 — flies emerged from drying flower heads on the window..

Material and methods

A series of tephritid flies was collected by IŠ in a room, where flower heads of marigolds (*Calendula*) were drying. He sent the pictures to Jozef Oboňa (University of Prešov), who identified them as *T. praecox*, asked VAK for verification and kindly sent them to Kyiv. Variability of

the wing pattern and size in the series was then examined by VAK. Material is deposited in the collection of the I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology (SIZK). Flies were photographed with Leica Z16 APO System through the kindness of Halyna Stetsun (SIZK). SVK provided general comments on morphology, distribution and taxonomy of this species and wrote most of the text.

Figs 4–6. *Tephritis praecox*: 4 — head, left, 5 — male, habitus, 6 — a torymid wasp, possible parasitoid of larvae / pupae.

***Tephritis praecox* (Loew, 1844) (Figs 3–20)**

Material examined. Slovakia, Trebišov, 48.607589°N, 21.718052°E, ex flower heads of *Calendula officinalis*, 14-17.10.2021, 15♂, 16♀ (I.Šalamon) (SIZK).

Tephritis praecox has not been recorded either in Czech Republic, or in Slovakia (Heřman & Kinkorová, 2009) yet, and was obviously introduced with the seed material purchased from a Czech company providing it. The flies are strictly oligophagous feeding only in *Calendula* spp. and having no other hosts in the wild nature. They are not severe pests of marigold flowers

used predominantly to prepare an alcohol-based tincture, which is an antiseptic and wound-healing remedy or used in homeopathy. However, it clearly can survive Middle-European winters especially due to the global warming and persistently occur in its planting areas for ornamental or medical purposes. They are neither otherwise harmful nor dangerous as invasion species, having very strict host specialization. However, its population may grow from year to year in plantations and needs to be controlled.

The chalcid wasps of the family Torymidae (probably a *Torymus* sp. — Fig. 6) reared from *Calendula* flower heads

Figs 7–16. *Tephritis praecox*, wings (left column — males, right column — females). Scale bar: 1 mm. Letters indicate variable characters mentioned in the text below. .

Figs 17–21 *Tephritis hurvitzii* (17–19 — male, 20–21 — female): 17 — abdomen, ventrally; 18 — epandrium, posterior, 19 — phallus glans; 20 — ovipositor; 21 — spermathecae (semi-schematic).

along with *T. praecox*, are apparently its parasitoids or hyperparasitoids, which can be natural enemies controlling *T. praecox* population.

The wing pattern of *T. praecox* may be variable in a few characters, which are often considered among important in the keys and diagnoses of *Tephritis*, but in this case, clearly showing variability (see Figs 7–16): a) pterostigma with hyaline spot or entirely dark (90% — 10%), b) cell r_{2+3} proximally of crossvein r-m with a hyaline spot or entirely dark (80% — 20%), c) hyaline spots at apex of cell r_{2+3} separated or fused (40% — 60%), d) hyaline dots aligned to crossvein r-m in cell br present or absent (80% — 20%), e) middle pair of hyaline spots in cell m_4 fused into single elongate spot or separate (70% — 30%).

Male genitalia (Figs 18–19) quite typical for the genus. Ovipositor: eversible membrane (Fig. 20) ventrally with moderately developed scales. Aculeus evenly tapered apically, without incisions or steps (Fig. 20). Spermatheca globose, with elongate neck longer than its apical part (Fig. 21).

References

- Heřman, P. & Kinkorová, J. 2009. Tephritidae Newman, 1834. In: Jedlička, L., Kúdela, M. & Stloukalová V. *Checklist of Diptera of the Czech Republic and Slovakia (electronic version 2, 2009)*. Faunima & Comenius University, Bratislava. Available at <http://www.edvis.sk/diptera2009/families/tephritidae.htm>. (Accessed 30.11.2021)
- Korneyev, S.V., Smit, J. T., Hulbert, D.L., Norrbom, A. L., Gaimari, S. D., Korneyev, V. A. 2020. Phylogeny of the genus *Tephritis* Latreille, 1804 (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Arthropod Systematics & Phylogeny*, 78: 111–132.
- Merz, B. & Korneyev, V. A. 2004. Tephritidae. In: Beuk, P. & Pape, T. (eds): *Fauna Europaea: Diptera. Fauna Europaea version 2017.06*, <https://fauna-eu.org> (Accessed 30.11.2021)
- Merz, B. 1992. The fruit flies of the Canary Islands (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Entomologia scandinavica*. 23: 215–231.
- Norrbom, A. L., Carroll, L. E., Thompson, F. C., White, I. M. & Freidberg, A. 1999. Systematic Database of Names. In: Thompson, F. C. (ed.) *Fruit Fly Expert Identification System and Systematic Information Database*. Backhuys Publishers, Leiden, 65–299.